

An Analysis of Incidence of COVID-19 in Patients Aged Less Than 75 Years in a Tertiary Care Hospital in North-East India

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Abstract:

Background: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) which is also called COVID-19 has had a profound impact on human lives, reshaping societies and altering the course of daily existence. The virus, which spread rapidly across the globe, led to widespread illness and a significant loss of life. Healthcare systems were strained, exposing vulnerabilities and prompting urgent adaptations.

Objective: The present study aimed to examine the incidence and possible association between age and gender among positive COVID-19 patients (aged <75 years), and to explore the possible reasons for variations observed across different age groups and genders.

Methods: This was a retrospective hospital based analytical study. After an elaborate consent process, nasopharyngeal & oropharyngeal swabs were collected in Viral Transport media (VTM) and sent to the testing laboratory for confirmation by nucleic acid-based reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). Descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests were done and significance of tests was decided at P=0.05.

Results: Data regarding patients details were collected in the hospital facility. A total of 94, 672 (Assam – 92,511 and Arunachal Pradesh-2161) samples were collected from patient's and tested for COVID-19 (October 2020 to March 2021). During this period a total of 2,210 positive cases were detected at the laboratory from Assam (n= 2,095, 94.8%) and Arunachal Pradesh (n= 115, 5.2%) respectively. Sonitpur district (n=1416) of Assam reported the highest number of positive cases followed by Udalguri district (n=306). Males (n=1761, 79.7 %) was affected more than females (n= 449, 20.3 %). In both male & female the age group which was affected the most was between 16-30 years and 31-45 years.

Conclusions: Early diagnosis by real time PCR has helped in the identification of the pathogen in individuals at an early stage, which has facilitated the containment of positive cases.

Key words: SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19, Psychological, Viral Transport Media, RT-PCR.

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Introduction

SARS-CoV-2 is a novel coronavirus that originated from Wuhan in the Hubei province of Central China and it has been linked to the massive outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome [1]. On December 31, 2019, the first case of COVID-19 was reported in humans and subsequently on March 11, 2020, World Health Organization (WHO) declared the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) as a global pandemic [2].

The overall current global incidence of COVID-19 at present (around 8th April 2021) is around 132,730,691 confirmed cases with a death cases of about 2,880,726 [3]. The overall confirmed and death cases reported from different countries are as follows [3]:

Country	Confirmed cases	Death
China	1,03,003	4,851
United Kingdom	43,67,295	1,26,927
United States of America	3,05,41,000	5,52,928
Italy	37,00,393	1,12,374
Russian Federation	46,14,834	1,01,845
Brazil	2,76,890	12,366

The first case of COVID-19 in India, was identified from Kerala on 30th January, 2020. Since then, the

number has been increasing steadily due to local transmission and foci of community transmission.

India has reported 12,928,574 confirmed COVID-19 cases with Death toll of 1,66,862 cases [3].

COVID-19 cases reported from other parts of India are as follows [4]:

State	Confirmed Cases	Death
Assam	2,19,272	1,112
Maharashtra	32,29,547	57,028
Kerala	11,48,948	4,729
Punjab	2,63,090	7,334
Tamil Nadu	9,15,386	12,840

Cases reported from neighboring countries of India are such as Sri Lanka confirmed cases 93,993 with a death case of 591, Nepal confirmed cases 278,768 with a death case of 3,038, Bangladesh confirmed cases 659,278 with death cases of 9,447 and Pakistan confirmed cases of 700,188 with a death cases of 15,026 [3].

Virus: SARS-CoV-2 Coronavirus are positive sense single stranded RNA viruses. They have an extensive wide range of natural hosts and can affect multiple systems [5,6]. The SARS-CoV-2 is a member of the Order Nidovirales, Coronaviridae Family, Genus Coronavirus, sub-family Orthocoronavirinae. It is further sub-divided into four genera, viz. Alphacoronavirus, Betacoronavirus, Gammacoronavirus and Deltacoronavirus [7,8]. These virus have characteristics club shaped spikes that project from their surface, and their size can vary from 26 – 32 kilobases.

Age is a critical factor in COVID-19 transmission, and it plays a pivotal role in framing guidelines and designing interventions to curb transmission in the population as a whole and projecting the expected global burden. The analysis of this study, together with early evidence, clearly suggest that there is a dependence of age in determining susceptibility and risk of developing clinical symptoms following infection with SARS-CoV-2.

SARS-CoV-2 has shown moderate transmissibility and relatively low pathogenicity. Although, COVID-19 has affected people across age groups, but older persons have been far more likely to suffer the most with severe health consequences. In human beings the Coronavirus infection commonly present with mild to severe respiratory diseases that are characterized by high fever, severe inflammation, cough and internal organ dysfunction that can even be fatal [9]. Early diagnosis by real-time PCR and next-generation sequencing has facilitated the identification of the pathogen at an early stage.

India, with a population of approximately 1.3 billion people, initially took some of the strictest measures to flatten the spiking curve of incidence & spread of coronavirus by enforcing administrative hammer and revamping healthcare infrastructures and resources. The nation witnessed

countrywide lockdown, usage of masks in public places, hand sanitization, segregation of affected person. The lockdown was effective and it was widely obeyed initially, but it could not be sustained as the economy was jeopardized. Thus the Government have to prioritize reopening and accepted the risks of surging coronavirus infections amidst increasing mortality. Though high efforts have been put on to counter this virus but sporadic incidence are still being reported till date.

The present study was an attempt to address the association between age and gender among positive COVID-19 cases (age < 75 years) and also to discuss the possible factors responsible for the variation among age categories and gender.

Material and Methods

Study Conduct: This study was conducted between October 2020 and March 2021. The patients were explained elaborately about the study in their native language and Consents of the patients were taken for collection of samples. Samples were collected from patients suspected for COVID-19 and who have travelled from affected countries as well as from other parts of the states. Strictest hygienic measures were undertaken during sample collection and requisite guidelines being followed for sample transport and storage. Details of the patients which include age, sex, travel history, symptoms etc were recorded in standard specimen referral forms as per ICMR guidelines.

Laboratory Confirmation: Nasopharyngeal & oropharyngeal swabs were collected in Viral Transport media (VTM) and sent to Viral Research & Diagnostics Laboratory, TMCH for RT-PCR test for detection of presence of SARS-CoV-2. Samples were tested for SARS-CoV-2 as per protocol (manufacturer guidelines) by using Viral RNA extraction kit and RT-PCR kits which was supplied by ICMR, New Delhi, India. Positive confirmed cases were shifted to isolation ward.

Data analysis: The data were analyzed by using latest version of PRISM Software. Descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests were done and significance of tests was decided at P=0.05.

Results

General Information: A total of 94,672 samples suspected for Covid-19 were tested at Virus Research and Diagnostic Laboratory (VRDL), TMCH during the period of October 2020 to March 2021. Data regarding patients' details were collected in hospital facility. Of the total samples tested, the state of Assam contributed a total of

92,511 samples and the state of Arunachal Pradesh contributed a total of 2161 samples (Table 1, Figure 1). During this period a total of 2,210 positive Covid-19 cases were detected at the laboratory from Assam (n= 2095, 94.8%) and Arunachal Pradesh (n=115, 5.2%) respectively (Table 2, Figure 2).

Table 1: Assessment of Positivity rate of Assam & Arunachal Pradesh

State	Samples tested	Positive cases	Percentage
Assam	92511	2095	2.26 %
Arunachal Pradesh	2161	115	5.32 %

Figure 1: Distribution of Samples: Assam: 92511, Arunachal Pradesh: 2161

Table 2: Distribution of COVID 19 Positive Cases in Assam & Arunachal Pradesh

State	Positive Cases	Percentage %
Arunachal Pradesh	115	5.20
Assam	2095	94.80
Districts of Assam	Positive Cases	Percentage %
Sonitpur	1416	64.07
Biswanath	88	3.98
Nagaon	57	2.58
Morigaon	43	1.94
Udalguri	306	13.85
Darrang	108	4.89
Kamrup	38	1.72
Arunachal Pradesh	115	5.20
Nalbari	12	0.54
Kokrajhar	9	0.41
Karbi Anglong	18	0.81

Figure 2: Distribution of Positive Cases between Assam & Arunachal Pradesh in the samples tested at VRDL, TMCH, between October 2020 – March 2021.

Sonitpur district carried the maximum load of confirmed positive Covid-19 cases:

Samples from 10 districts of Assam and some samples from Arunachal Pradesh were tested at the VRDL laboratory. The samples included people having travel history and with no travel history.

Out of the 2210 total Covid-19 cases detected, Sonitpur district was found to be the most affected district with 64.07 %, (n= 1416) of the total cases which was followed by Udalguri district with 13.85 %, (n= 306) of the total cases. The other district showed variable distribution of the positive cases (Table 2, Figure 3).

Figure 3: District-wise distribution of Positive Cases in Assam & Arunachal Pradesh

Younger aged people were most susceptible to Covid-19 disease:

Our observation revealed a rather different but interesting finding. Of all the positive COVID-19 cases that were detected in the laboratory, younger aged people were found to be more vulnerable to the disease. It may be noted that people aged between 16-30 yrs and 31-45 years showed the

maximum spike in the positive cases in both males and females and significantly associated with the disease (p value = 0.0180). Interestingly, out of the 2210 confirmed positive patients, only 103 cases were detected in the age group 61 - 75 years and understandably there was no significance association found in this age group (p value = 0.8953). (Table 4, Figure 4).

Table 3: Age wise distribution

Age	Patients	Percentage %
0-15	100	4.52
16-30	947	42.85
31-45	725	32.80
46-60	335	15.16
61-75	103	4.66
Total	2210	

Table 4: Age & Gender wise distribution

Age	Male	Female
0-15	74	26
16-30	776	171
31-45	576	149
46-60	254	81
61-75	81	22
Total	1761	449

Figure 4: Age and Gender wise Distribution of Covid-19 Cases. The positivity ratio between male and female was seen to be approximately 4:1 showing that males were more vulnerable to the disease as compared to females.

Figure 5: Age wise Distribution of Covid-19 Cases. The positivity is highest in the age group of 16-30 years followed by 31-45 years. Positivity is lowest in 0-15 years and 61-75 years.

Females were less susceptible to COVID-19 as compared to males:

Of the 2210 confirmed positive cases that were detected during the study period, a total of 1761 (79.7%) patients were male and only 449, (20.3%) patients were females. The above observations showed that males contracted the disease almost 4 times more than that of females (Table 4, Figure 6).

Figure 6: Distribution of COVID 19 Cases among males and females in Assam & Arunachal Pradesh

Discussion

Our study demonstrated interesting trajectories of the COVID-19 cases in patient's based on gender and age groups. Our observation revealed that of all the positive COVID-19 cases that were detected at the laboratory, younger aged people were found to be more vulnerable to the disease. It may be noted that people aged between 16-30 yrs and 31-45 yrs showed the maximum spike in the positive cases in both males and females and significantly associated with the disease (p value = 0.0180). Interestingly, out of the 2210 confirmed positive patients, only 103 cases were detected in the age group 61-75 yrs and understandably there was no significance association found in this age group (p value = 0.8953). In our study the gender which was affected more was Males (n=1761, 79.7 %) than females (n= 449, 20.3 %). The above observations showed that males contracted the disease almost 4 times more than that of females First case of COVID-19 was detected in the month of May 2020 which was followed by gradual increase in the positive cases.

In a recent study, man accounted for 55.4% of COVID 19 positive cases and women accounted for 44.6% COVID-19 cases [10]. According to ICMR, approximately 34 per cent of infected people in India are under the age of 30 years. According to experts, higher COVID-19 infections among younger Indian population is directly linked to the population ratio [11]. In a study conducted in the U.S., 60.3% of 5700 hospitalized COVID-19 patients were found to be males. [12]. The findings analysed in this study were consistent with other

reports, in which younger people accounted for most confirmed COVID-19 cases [13, 14, 15].

While older people and those with pre-existing medical issues including obesity, diabetes, and hypertension were initially highlighted as being particularly vulnerable to COVID-19 infection and death, our observation showed an intriguing but rather different conclusion. Younger adults were shown to be more susceptible to the disease out of all the positive COVID-19 instances that were identified in the lab.

However, there are a number of reasons for this, such as increased viral exposure from more outdoor activities, the return of migrant workers to the state, immunological differences based on sex determined by X chromosome and sex hormone, gender behavior (lifestyle), which includes higher rates of drinking and smoking in men than in women, and a more careless attitude in men than in women when it comes to frequent hand washing, wearing face masks, and staying at home orders. Children also had the lowest disease burden, maybe as a result of the early school closings and vacations that occurred during that time. Nevertheless, more validation using a greater number of samples and regional epidemiology investigations is required.

At all ages, there are gender differences in the frequency and outcomes of infectious diseases, with males generally carrying a higher burden of bacterial, viral, fungal, and parasitic infections. [16-19]. Previous coronavirus outbreaks MERS-CoV and SARS CoV have also been found to infect more men than women [20, 21]. The Saudi Arabian

MERS outbreak in 2013 - 2014 exhibited a case fatality rate of 52% in men and 23% in women [22]. These findings imply that, even though socioeconomic variables might be affecting some elements of the pandemic, the considerable sex-bias linked to the COVID-19 pandemic is most likely caused by basic differences in the immune response between males and females. The female advantage in COVID-19 may be explained by previously documented sex differences in the innate and adaptive immune systems. Within the adaptive immune system, females have higher numbers of CD4+ T cells [23-27], more robust CD8+ T cell cytotoxic activity, and increased B cell production of immunoglobulin compared to males [23, 28]. Women may be less susceptible to infection because of the X chromosome and sex hormones, which have been shown to have an impact on both innate and adaptive immunity. [29].

Less severe etiology but stronger transmission competence are characteristics of COVID-19, as evidenced by the steadily rising number of confirmed cases worldwide. Early diagnosis by next-generation sequencing and real-time PCR has made it easier to identify the pathogen early on, which has made it easier to contain positive cases. With robust policies from the central and state governments, we seek to contain the spread and effects of COVID-19 in the future.

The COVID 19 pattern point to the possibility of future CoV outbreaks brought on by climatic changes, and ecological factors may be connected to interactions between humans and animals. As anticipated, SARS-CoV-2 outbreak was contained just like the previous epidemics. The real concern, though, is how we intend to combat the next zoonotic CoV pandemic, which is probably going to happen in the next five to ten years, or maybe even sooner.

Conclusion

The recent SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has taught us all a valuable lesson and acted as a timely reminder of how quickly emerging, mutating, and spreading novel diseases can cause worldwide public health emergencies.

This study sheds light on the relationship between gender and age and COVID-19 cases, as it was discovered that younger age groups in both males and females were the most impacted. More men than women were impacted. Because of the early lockdown and the application of all preventive measures to control the spread of disease, fewer positive cases were observed in this area of Assam.

The biological variables (immunological and genetic differences) may account for the variation in infection rate and recovery chances across age and gender. Investigations on human replication,

transmission dynamics, and disease should be carried out further. In the near future, it will aid in the development of possible treatments against zoonotic CoV epidemics. We are hoping that by enacting robust age- and gender-specific public health policies by the central and state governments, we can reduce the incidence and effects of COVID-19 infections.

Author Contributions

All the authors substantially contributed to the conception, design, analysis and interpretation of data, checking and approving the final version of the manuscript and agree to be accountable for its contents.

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Conflict of interest statement

We declare that we have no conflict of interest.

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